

Inference engine for custom neural networks with oneAPI

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

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A recent effort to explore a neural network inference in FPGAs focusing on low-latency applications in triggering subsystems of the LHC, which would enable searches for new dark sector particles and novel measurements of the Higgs boson, resulted in a firmware implementation of machine learning algorithms using High-Level Synthesis language (HLS) for FPGAs, called hls4ml. Deep Learning algorithms using the hls4ml framework have quite impressive performance on FPGAs, but do not work well on contemporary architectures, like CPUs. To enable the possibility of using hls4ml models in High Level Trigger for CPUs, we explore usage of Intel oneAPI Toolkits in the hls4ml framework. We design, implement and integrate the inference engine with oneAPI into the hls4ml, and show that it can accelerate over hundreds of times the inference time for CPUs, if the data parallelism is exploited.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In past years Deep Learning algorithms have proven its utility in classification, regression, and reconstruction tasks. A typical Deep Learning algorithm often comprises multiple operations, such as matrix multiplication, convolutions, and other tensor operations, which are computationally demanding. Having a farm of CPUs can rapidly decrease the latency of processing Deep Learning algorithms if the software is highly optimized. Optimizing the software in a hardware-aware way for Deep Learning tasks can be cumbersome. This is where Intel oneAPI Base Toolkit can be applied. The oneAPI toolkit consists of a core set of tools and libraries for building and deploying high-performance, data-centric applications across diverse architectures. Building Deep Learning algorithms with oneAPI gives certainty that software is highly optimized with the best performance for Intel hardware architectures.

At the CERN Large Hadron Collider (LHC), the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment collects signals generated by the particles produced in high-energy proton collisions that occur every 25ns. It means that LHC generates 40 million samples of data per second and in terms of storage it is up to a petabyte of data per second. Such a huge amount of data can't be stored, because the data centers would run out of memory pretty fast. This is why the incoming collisions in LHC are processed in real-time by the so-called trigger system. The trigger system is structured as a combination of two hierarchical layers: the hardware trigger running on FPGAs (also called L1 trigger) operating with a latency of 10 μ s, selecting around 100K events/sec, and the software trigger running on a CPU farm (also called High Level Trigger, HLT) selecting around 1K events/sec to be stored for later analysis.

Recently, an effort to deploy a neural network on the L1 trigger was started. The research for neural network inference in FPGAs, which would enable searches for new dark sector particles and novel measurements of the Higgs boson, resulted in a firmware implementation of machine learning algorithms using High-Level Synthesis language (HLS) for FPGAs, called hls4ml. The hls4ml models do pretty well resulting in latency on the scale of 100ns on FPGAs. Despite good performance on FPGA hardware, the hls4ml algorithms are very inefficient on CPUs, which makes them inapplicable for HLT trigger. This project offers a solution to that problem. We propose an inference engine using oneAPI Toolkit resulting in high-performance Deep Learning algorithms on Intel CPUs. Using oneAPI backend in hls4ml, the user can easily lower the hls4ml model's latency hundreds of times and make the model appropriate to run in the software trigger of the LHC experiment.

2. MACHINE LEARNING INFERENCE WITH HLS4ML

The hls4ml is a companion compiler, which translates Machine Learning models from common open-source software packages such as Keras and PyTorch into RTL (Register-Transfer Level) abstraction for FPGAs using High-Level Synthesis tools, which have demonstrated considerable progress in recent years. The hls4ml tool allows physicists to rapidly prototype Machine Learning algorithms for both firmware feasibility and physics performance without extensive Verilog/VHDL experience, thus greatly decreasing the time for algorithm development cycles while preserving engineering resources.

The hls4ml main design purpose is to run ML algorithms on FPGAs with high-performance. The hls4ml model has its intermediate representation between Python model and HLS synthesis, which is not fully optimized C++ code possible to run on CPU. However, the hls4ml framework was not designed to run the algorithms on different types of hardware, thus the performance of hls4ml models on CPUs is bad. According to that, there is a growing need to design new backend in the hls4ml framework with high-performance implementation of ML algorithms for CPUs to make the models applicable in HLT trigger and offline computations. To do so we decided to use Intel oneAPI Base Toolkit.

The workflow of hls4ml with an expanded oneAPI backend is illustrated in Figure 1. The appended oneAPI backend is present within a blue dotted line. Currently, the workflow is divided into three parts: red, purple, and gray. The red one indicates the usual software workflow required to design a deep learning algorithm for a specific task. This, using tools such as Keras and PyTorch, involves a training step and possible compression, including quantization and pruning, before settling on a final model. The purple section of the workflow is the task of hls4ml, which translates a model into an HLS project that can be synthesized and implemented on an FPGA (the gray section). Here also comes the appended section with oneAPI backend. Instead of translating a model into an HLS project, we translate it into a Data Parallel C++ (DPC++) Project that can be deployed on diverse Intel architectures including CPUs, GPU Xe architectures, and in the future AI Accelerators. Since CERN data-centers mainly consist of CPUs, we are focusing in this project on deploying the algorithms on CPUs, however, we recall that the DPC++ project is not limited to CPUs and can be deployed on different architectures.

Figure 1. The hls4ml workflow to translate a model either into FPGA implementation using Vivado backend or Data Parallel C++ project using oneAPI backend.

3. ONEAPI INFERENCE ENGINE

In this section we describe in detail basic concepts, what oneAPI backend consists of, a library which we used to build the backend, and how to build new custom deep learning algorithms using that backend.

a. ONEAPI BASIC CONCEPTS

Nowadays, software development for CPUs and accelerators requires different languages, libraries, and tools. That means each hardware platform requires completely separate software investments and provides limited application code reusability across different target architectures.

The oneAPI programming model simplifies the programming of CPUs and accelerators using modern C++ features to express parallelism with a programming language called Data Parallel C++ (DPC++). The DPC++ language enables code reuse for the host (such as a CPU) and accelerators (such as a GPU) using a single source language, with execution and memory dependencies clearly communicated. Mapping within the DPC++ code can be used to transition the application to run on the hardware, or set of hardware, that best accelerates the workload. We decided to use oneAPI Toolkit in this project not only to enable reusability of software generated by oneAPI backend in case, when new hardware replaces the old one but also to ensure that operations running on specific accelerators are highly optimized and meet a latency required at CMS Experiment in High Energy Physics. The general concept of using oneAPI is illustrated in Figure 2, which in a nutshell shows what oneAPI consists of and what it is intended for.

Figure 2. Intel oneAPI Toolkits basic concept illustration. [1]

b. ONEDNN LIBRARY

Intel oneAPI Toolkit includes lots of libraries designed for specific tasks e.g. Intel oneAPI Math Kernel Library (oneMKL) for the development of high-performance operations or another library Intel VTune Profiler for performance analysis. In this particular project, we focus on developing an inference engine for custom neural networks, which are a subset of Deep Learning algorithms, so we decided to use Intel oneAPI Deep Neural Network Library (oneDNN).

The oneDNN library is an open-source performance library for deep learning applications. It includes basic building blocks for neural networks optimized for Intel Architecture Processors and Intel GPUs. OneDNN is intended for deep learning applications and framework developers interested in improving application

performance on Intel CPUs and GPUs. It supports C and C++ interfaces, OpenMP, Intel oneAPI Threading Building Blocks, and OpenCL runtimes.

The oneDNN library comes with a programming model, which consists of abstractions such as engine, stream, primitives, and memory objects. The relationship between all of these entities is briefly presented in Figure 3, which also includes additional concepts relevant to oneDNN programming model, such as primitive attributes and descriptors. In essence, the engine, which is an abstraction of a device on which the algorithms are deployed, executes one or several primitives (operations) to process data in one or several memory objects in the context of the stream. For more detailed information about oneDNN library refer to oneDNN documentation [2].

Figure 3. Overview of oneDNN programming model. Blue rectangles denote oneDNN objects and red lines denote dependencies between objects. [3]

c. MODEL DEPLOYMENT USING INTEL DEVCLOUD

Once a deep learning algorithm is implemented using oneDNN it needs to be tested correctly. To do so we use the Intel DevCloud, which is a development sandbox for data center to edge workloads. It gives a possibility to develop, test, and run your workloads on a cluster of the latest Intel hardware and software. There are several hardware architectures available in the DevCloud such as Intel CPUs (6th to 8th generation and Xeon processors), GPUs, VPUs (Neural Compute Stick 2, Movidius Vision Processing Unit), and FPGAs (Arria 10). Also, the whole oneAPI Toolkit is preinstalled there.

Using Intel DevCloud we are sure that we make full use of the tested hardware and no other user utilizes the hardware. We connect to the DevCloud using both JupyterLab HTTP connection and Visual Studio Code Remote Server, develop our algorithms, and test it using tools available in the sandbox. A detailed illustration of how Intel DevCloud works is presented in Figure 4. A user connects to the development server using HTTP connection, can store up to 50GB of data (you can also request for more), schedule a job using qsub job scheduler, receive the results and analyze them. The use of Intel DevCloud is free of charge and only needs pre registration.

Figure 4. An algorithm deployment workflow using Intel DevCloud. [4]

d. ONEDNN NEURAL NETWORK CONSTRUCTION

In this subsection, we describe how to construct a neural network using oneDNN library. In particular, we explain how to create oneDNN memory objects, create oneDNN primitives (here fully connected layer), and execute the primitives.

To start using oneDNN, firstly, we must include *dnnl.hpp* header file in the program, so all required objects and functions are available. Once we include the header we can initialize an engine and engine stream described in subsection b. With that, we also need to declare a neural network to store the primitives and primitive attributes. We do that in the following:

```
dnnl::engine eng(dnnl::engine::kind::cpu, 0);
dnnl::stream engine_stream(eng);
std::vector<dnnl::primitive> net;
std::vector<std::unordered_map<int, dnnl::memory>> net_args;
```

Once the engine is initialized we can create memory objects that will store input data, weights, biases, and output data. All of the objects are attached to the specified engine. For example, we create a memory for input data in the following:

```
dnnl::memory::dims input_data_dims = {1, 16};
auto input_data_memory = dnnl::memory({
    {input_data_dims},
    dnnl::memory::data_type::f32,
    dnnl::memory::format_tag::ab},
    eng);
auto input_data_md = dnnl::memory::desc({
    {input_data_dims},
    dnnl::memory::data_type::f32,
    dnnl::memory::format_tag::any});
```

In this example, the format tag specified as *ab* means that input data will be stored in memory as a plain 2D tensor in *NC* format (batch, input features). In the same way, we create data for weights, biases, and output data. For detailed information about creating oneDNN memory and which format to use please refer to oneDNN documentation [2].

After initializing memory for all necessary objects we can create a descriptor and primitive descriptor for a layer which we are going to add to the network. Here we create a fully connected layer, which in oneDNN primitives is represented as an inner product primitive. We create an inner product descriptor with specifying propagation kind as a forward inference to optimize the primitive for inference execution and omit computations that are necessary only for backpropagation. If we initialized memory descriptors for input, weights, biases, and output as *input_data_md*, *fc1_weights_md*, *fc1_bias_md* and *fc1_output_md*, we can declare the primitive in the following:

```
auto fc1_desc = dnnl::inner_product_forward::desc(
    dnnl::prop_kind::forward_inference,
    input_data_md, fc1_weights_md, fc1_bias_md, fc1_output_md);

auto fc1_prim_desc = dnnl::inner_product_forward::primitive_desc(fc1_desc, eng);
```

Once the primitive is initialized, we can add it to the network:

```
net.push_back(dnnl::inner_product_forward(fc1_prim_desc));
net_args.push_back({{DNNL_ARG_SRC, input_data_memory},
    {DNNL_ARG_WEIGHTS, fc1_weights_memory},
    {DNNL_ARG_BIAS, fc1_bias_memory},
    {DNNL_ARG_DST, fc1_memory}});
```

After all required primitives are created and added to the network, we can execute the network in the following:

```
net.push_back(dnnl::inner_product_forward(fc1_prim_desc));
for (size_t i=0; i<net.size(), ++i)
    net.at(i).execute(engine_stream, net_args.at(i))
engine_stream.wait();
```

The network is executed so we can read the results from output data memory and all of the experiment is done. For more detailed examples please refer to oneDNN documentation examples [2] or this project repository [5].

e. CUSTOM NEURAL NETWORKS

In the previous subsection, it is described how to construct a layer in a neural network from existing primitives. Novel deep learning algorithms (e.g. graph neural networks) have no such a representation in oneDNN primitives. To implement those algorithms with a highly optimized code the algorithm's operations have to be mapped in detail to oneDNN primitives. In this subsection, we present an example of how to build a custom neural network (here graph neural network) using oneDNN library.

Graph neural networks (GNNs) are gaining interest in High Energy Physics applications, mainly due to their intrinsic value when dealing with sparse input datasets, which are very common in HEP [6]. GNNs are designed to provide competitive performance on particle reconstruction tasks while efficiently dealing with data sparsity. These architectures aim to keep a trainable space representation at minimal computational costs. GNNs have proved its utility and are crucial for R&D of CMS Experiment. That's why we explore GNNs implementation using oneDNN and propose a solution to that. In particular, we investigate a specific example of GNNs, GarNet [7]. More information about a recent review of applications of GNNs to HEP problems may be found in Ref. [8].

A GarNet layer is a graph neural block that can be split into three parts: input transformation, aggregation, and output transformation. The input transformation can be expressed as two neural networks executed in parallel: an encoder network and a distance calculator network. In the aggregation part, the output of the encoder is weighted by a potential function and averaged across vertices. In the last stage, output

transformation, the aggregated features are retransformed with the same potential function and sent to a single-layer decoder network, which transforms the data into the final output representation. In a nutshell, a GarNet layer takes as input a $B \times V \times F_{IN}$ data set, consisting of a batch of B examples, each represented by a set of V (vertices) detector hits and F_{IN} input features, and returns the same set of data with F_{out} output features. Inside the layer F_{IN} features of each vertex are encoded into an internal representation F_{LR} and gathered at S aggregators.

To develop a highly optimized code for GarNet we propose a representation of the layer using only oneDNN primitives. In Figure 5. we illustrated a detailed representation of GarNet operations using oneDNN with respect to the shape of processed data. The input transformation part can be easily expressed as two inner product primitives, which in oneDNN syntax are fully connected layers. The computation of potential function can be replaced with two elementwise operations: eltwise pow with parameter $\alpha = -1$ and $\beta = 2$. The aggregation part we found as a Matrix Multiplication (MatMul) primitive across V dimension with bias equal to zero and elementwise linear operation with parameter $\alpha = 1/V_{max}$ and $\beta = 0$. In the last stage, the output transformation can be replaced with a Binary Multiplication primitive and the decoder just like the encoder with inner product primitive. To preserve shapes of processing data and do the multiplications across correct dimensions there is a need to do also some reorders primitives of shape in memory, which also are added to the workflow. In the end, we have a working GarNet layer implemented using: 3 inner product primitives, 3 element-wise primitives, matrix multiplication primitive, binary multiplication primitive and 3 reorders.

Figure 5. A GarNet layer workflow with usage of oneDNN primitives.

4. RESULTS

In this section we describe parts already integrated into the hls4ml framework, present results acquired using the integrated backend, and explain the utility of the project.

a. SUPPORTED PRIMITIVES IN HLS4ML ONEAPI BACKEND

Most of the project consists of coding an infrastructure to enable oneAPI backend in the hls4ml package. There was an extensive effort to understand as well hls4ml framework as oneAPI Toolkits. In the end, the inference engine has been built on top of oneDNN library and integrated to the hls4ml framework with several supported primitives, which enables hls4ml model translation to the DPC++ project. We also added a possibility to process data in batches using oneAPI backend, which is currently unavailable in hls4ml using other backends.

Primitives supported in hls4ml oneAPI backend:

- Dense layers (inner product primitive);
- Activation functions such as ReLU, tanh, log, linear, exp, sqrt and many others (element-wise primitives);
- Softmax primitive;
- Convolution primitive;
- Pooling primitives (MaxPooling, AveragePooling).

With an integrated inference engine in the hls4ml we test all supported primitives in Intel DevCloud on Intel Xeon Gold 6128 processor, which has a 3.40GHz processing frequency, 6 cores, and 19.25MB of L3 Cache. Also, we compare the results with current hls4ml implementation for CPU and Keras/Tensorflow(TF) of the same network and show oneDNN acceleration. Tests have been done for two scenarios: Jet Tagging Task and MNIST Digit Classification with convolutional layers.

b. JET TAGGING TASK

In this scenario, we take a physics problem of substructure-based jet tagging as a benchmark, on which there is a rich literature of deep learning applications [9]. In this context, there were attempts to use CNNs, RNNs, as well as physics-inspired network architectures. Jets have been represented as grayscale images, RGB images, sequences of particles, or set of physics-inspired high-level features, as we do in this scenario. We take the hls4ml LHC Jet dataset of high-pT jets from simulations of LHC proton-proton collisions [10] prepared for fastML/hls4ml studies. Input data of the dataset consists of 16 high level features to identify the 5 jet classes: quark (q), gluon (g), W boson (w), Z boson (z), or top quark (t).

In this case, we propose neural network architecture consisting of 3 hidden fully connected layers illustrated in Figure 6. We split the data into test and train datasets, that gives us over 166000 samples of testing data, train the model, and acquire 75.05% test accuracy. After all, we convert the model to a hls4ml model, test it on specified CPUs and compare the results.

Figure 6. Jet Tagging Task fully connected neural network architecture.

Measuring a latency of the current hls4ml model for CPU, hls4ml model with oneDNN backend, and Keras representation of the specified model, we collect the data and present it in Figure 7. In this case, we observe that if we are processing one sample at a time the current hls4ml backend does quite well compared to other ones and the reason here is that there is not much data to process (only 16 features at a time), so data parallelism is not applied here. However, if we can accumulate the data and process 166000 samples at a time, the difference between the current hls4ml backend for CPU and oneAPI backend is huge. We can observe in Figure 7. even 195 times acceleration over the current hls4ml backend. The Keras representation also does quite well. However, it needs to be noted that the Tensorflow version used in all of those

benchmarks were not compiled for this specific hardware. In this case, the Keras representation could speed up to 300%, if compiled for Intel Xeon 6128, but it still would be slower than oneDNN model.

Figure 7. Jet Tagging Task Neural Network inference time with available backends.

For more detailed information about the execution time of the model, we investigate how much time took particular operation while executing oneDNN implementation. To do so we put wall times before and after writing the data into Deep Neural Network Library (DNNL) memory. The results are presented in Figure 8. We observe that writing and reading from memory take a small amount of time with respect to executing the neural network. If the input data is much bigger than the output data (number of input features), we observe that writing out scales reading from memory, which is reasonable.

OneDNN library also comes with a lot of performance profiling and inspection tools. Using a performance profiling tool we investigate how much time was spent for a specific primitive while executing the network. To do so we compile the model with correct verbosity mode and collect the results. Detailed numbers of execution time are available in Figure 9. We observe that inner products take much more time to execute rather than ReLU or Softmax. In the test for batch size 166000, the first inner product execution time grows exponentially. The reason for that can be that the memory propagation of such huge data takes most of the

time for the first primitive. It may give us a conclusion, that there is a field to optimize the execution time of the model and do the memory propagation task in the compilation phase.

Figure 8. OneDNN execution time split into writing, reading and inferencing the data.

Figure 9. OneDNN execution time over specific primitives for batch size 1 and batch size 166000.

In the end, we also measure how much time it takes the model to process whole test data for different batch sizes. Because of the fact that there is no feature of processing data in batches in current hls4ml implementation, we stop comparing to that and prepare the chart only for oneAPI backend and Keras/TF version in Figure 10. In this case, we observe that oneDNN backend in hls4ml is better in 2 up to 5 times with respect to the Keras one, which could be reduced if Tensorflow was compiled for Intel Xeon 6128. We also observe that the execution time saturates on a certain level and there is not much gain in latency while processing bigger and bigger batch sizes. Detailed numbers of execution time have been added in a table to Figure 10.

Figure 10. Jet Tagging Task inference time over different batch sizes.

c. MNIST DIGIT CLASSIFICATION

In this scenario, we take a common digit classification problem using MNIST dataset. We test our model on this dataset to show that convolutional layers are working correctly in the integrated oneAPI inference engine and check how much can we gain using oneDNN backend for convolutional layers, which are more computationally demanding than pure fully connected layers.

We propose a model containing 2 convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters and ReLU activation functions. After each convolution, we apply max pooling layers. At the end of the model, we add a fully connected layer and softmax to finally classify the digit. The architecture of the model is presented in Figure 11. We split the dataset into test and training data, which gives us 10000 test image samples. After training the model, we acquire 96.86% accuracy on test data and finally, we deploy the model on Intel DevCloud.

Figure 11. A proposed digit classification model using convolutional layers for MNIST dataset.

We measure the latency for this model using the same techniques as we do in Jet Tagging Task. Data collected from benchmarks are presented in Figure 12. We observe that oneDNN backend integrated into hls4ml is much faster than the current implementation of hls4ml for CPUs and even better than Keras/TF implementation. We experience even 167.5 times faster inference time using oneDNN backend in hls4ml for batch size 1. If we increase the batch size, the acceleration grows rapidly. In the best case, for batch size 256, it takes only 0.2029s to process 10000 test samples using oneDNN. It means that we can

accelerate current hls4ml implementation for CPUs even 3763 times using oneDNN for this specific case. More detailed numbers of how batch size impacts the processing time of the model both for oneDNN and Keras are presented in Figure 13.

Figure 12. Convolutional neural network for MNIST dataset inference time over available backends for batch size 1.

Figure 13. Convolutional neural network for MNIST dataset inference time over different batch sizes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

There is no doubt that software using oneDNN primitives for deep learning algorithms can optimize the execution time. We have proved its utility in this project and integrated it into the hls4ml framework. The hls4ml framework was not designed to run deep learning algorithms on CPUs, but using this integrated oneAPI backend it surely can be utilized to deploy the algorithms on CPUs and what is more, be a part of HLT trigger in the CMS detector. For reference to the integrated inference engine in hls4ml backend, please visit a [github repository](#) [5].

6. PATHS OF FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The work done in this project opens other opportunities for development in hls4ml oneAPI backend. The major one is to support all primitives available in oneDNN library to the framework, another can be enabling quantization in models, which is crucial for neural network inference or testing the DPC++ models on other Intel architectures. Because of the fact that the whole infrastructure of oneAPI is now built in the hls4ml framework, it will be easier to go through all of these paths of the project's development.

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